

Unravelling the Nexus: Corruption in Electoral Funding and its Impact on Economic Development in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

Henshaw Okon Thompson¹

Dorn Cklaimz Enamhe²

Emmanuel Etim Samuel¹

Nse George Frank¹

¹Department of Sociology & Anthropology

University of Uyo

henshawthompson19@gmail.com

emmmansam2020@gmail.com

²Department of Social Works

University of Calabar

Dorncklaimz@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

This study explores the nexus between corruption in electoral funding and its impact on economic development in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Utilizing a mixed-methods approach, the research assesses the prevalence of corruption in electoral funding and its relationship with economic outcomes. The population of the study was made up of farmers, students, civil servants, businessmen, applicants, artisans, self-employed, contractors, religious leaders, politicians, etc. and were drawn from three (3) Local Government Areas sampled from the three (3) Senatorial Districts of Akwa Ibom State between ages 15-64. Data was collected using a structured questionnaire designed by the researchers. Statistical tools used to analyze the quantitative data were Chi-Square, while thematic analysis was applied to qualitative information. The findings indicate a significant connection between corruption in electoral funding and hindered economic development. The erosion of public trust, distortion in resource allocation, and compromised governance quality are identified as key consequences. The study recommends strengthening regulatory frameworks, enhancing civic education, institutional strengthening, legal reforms, and promoting public engagement to mitigate the adverse effects of corruption in electoral funding.

KEYWORDS: Corruption, Electoral funding, and Economic development

INTRODUCTION

Corruption in electoral funding represents a pervasive challenge that undermines the democratic fabric and economic development of regions worldwide. Akwa Ibom State, as a

vital component of the Nigerian federation, grapples with the complex interplay between corrupt electoral practices and its economic trajectory. The integrity of electoral processes directly influences the governance structures and subsequent economic outcomes of the state. This article aims to unravel the intricate connections between corruption in electoral funding and its implications for the economic development of Akwa Ibom State.

Corruption, in the context of electoral funding, refers to the illicit practices that compromise the transparency, fairness, and legitimacy of the electoral process. It manifests through activities such as vote buying, embezzlement of campaign funds, and the influence of undisclosed financial interests on political decisions. Understanding the nexus between corruption in electoral funding and economic development is imperative for devising effective strategies to foster sustainable growth and equitable governance.

As posited by Asuquo and Ekanem (2023), In Nigeria, the government recognizes the threat that corruption poses to the nation's economy and as a result, has taken some steps to address the problem. In Nigeria, some progress has been made by anti-corruption agencies, namely, the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC), the Independent Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Commission (ICPC), the Code of Conduct Bureau (CCB) and the Code of Conduct Tribunal (CCT), these agencies have become revitalized and more proactive in the pursuit of perpetrators of corrupt practices, irrespective of their social status and political persuasion. This is a radical departure from the past. Notwithstanding, Nigeria is still struggling to translate its policies and comparatively strong legislative framework into practice on the ground.

Akwa Ibom State has faced persistent challenges related to corruption in electoral funding, raising concerns about the legitimacy of political processes and the impact on economic development. The inflow of unregulated funds into electoral campaigns can compromise the integrity of the electoral system, potentially leading to policy decisions influenced by financial interests rather than the welfare of the citizens. Asuquo and Ekanem (2023), observe that political contests in Nigeria are characterized by desperation and violent struggle for political power among politicians. Recurring political violence in Nigeria could be attributed to the overzealousness and desperation of political gladiators to win elections or remain in office at all costs, and this desperation has impacted electoral funding. On this backdrop, this work sought to examine Corruption in Electoral Funding and its Impact on Economic Development in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- i. What is the prevalence of corruption in electoral funding in Akwa Ibom State?
- ii. What is the relationship between corruption in electoral funding and economic development in Akwa Ibom State?

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

- i. Ho1: There is no significant relationship between corruption in electoral funding and economic development in Akwa Ibom State.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Corruption and its Impact on Democratic Processes

Numerous scholars have explored the detrimental effects of corruption on democratic

processes. As Rose-Ackerman (1999) argues, corruption erodes public trust in government institutions, diminishing the legitimacy of elected officials. In the Nigerian context, Aiyede (2006) notes that corruption in electoral processes perpetuates a cycle of weak governance, hindering the effective implementation of policies crucial for economic development. Udonwa, Effiong, Asuquo and Samuel (2022), argue that corruption impedes economic development, the growth of democratic institutions, and the ability of developing countries to plan appropriately.

Corruption, a pervasive phenomenon in various societies, holds profound implications for democratic processes. In the realm of politics, corruption refers to the misuse of power, typically involving bribery, embezzlement, or other illicit practices, which undermines the principles of transparency, accountability, and fairness. Understanding the impact of corruption on democratic processes is essential for comprehending the broader challenges it poses to governance structures and the overall health of democracies.

Asuquo and Ekanem (2023), argue that corruption has affected many countries all over the world, especially developing countries. It has various implications for both the developed and developing economies. Corruption hampers development and thus raises the level of poverty in any economy that finds itself entrenched in corrupt practices. Corruption is a serious crime in Nigeria and it is punishable by the law. One of the primary consequences of corruption in democratic processes is the erosion of public trust. Rose-Ackerman (1999) emphasizes that when citizens perceive their elected officials engaging in corrupt practices, it engenders scepticism about the legitimacy and effectiveness of democratic institutions. Public trust is the bedrock of a functioning democracy, and its erosion can lead to a decline in civic engagement, voter turnout, and overall participation in democratic processes. Corruption also distorts the allocation of resources within a democratic system. As political decisions become influenced by personal gain rather than the public interest, the allocation of funds, development projects, and public services may deviate from the needs of the citizens. This distortion can exacerbate social inequalities and hinder the equitable distribution of resources, impeding the democratic ideal of representing the interests of the entire populace.

According to Asuquo and Ekanem (2023), Corruption can create a vicious cycle. A poorly educated population may be more susceptible to corruption, perpetuating a culture of dishonesty and undermining the foundations of a transparent and accountable society. This, in turn, can deter potential investors and hinder the growth of businesses in the state. Moreover, corruption introduces a corrosive element into the electoral process itself. The financing of political campaigns becomes susceptible to illicit contributions and questionable financial practices, compromising the integrity of the democratic competition. Vote buying, embezzlement of campaign funds, and other corrupt activities can distort the will of the electorate, subverting the democratic principle of free and fair elections.

In the long term, the impact of corruption on democratic processes extends to the quality of governance. Aiyede (2006) argues that corrupt practices create a vicious cycle of weak governance, where leaders prioritize personal gains over public welfare. This skewed decision-making process can impede effective policy implementation, hinder economic development, and perpetuate a culture of corruption within government institutions. According to Samuel, Asuquo, Thompson and Nya (2023), Women as wives, mothers and caregivers understand most of the weight of various challenges like corruption facing the human world. This is because, they have been at the receiving ends of these social, economic,

political, leadership, and war crises. Corruption also poses a threat to the rule of law, a cornerstone of democratic societies. When public officials engage in corrupt practices with impunity, it undermines the credibility and effectiveness of legal and judicial systems. This erosion of the rule of law weakens the democratic framework, making it challenging to hold the powerful accountable for their actions. Asuquo, Bassey, Samuel, Daniel and Usoro (2022) believe that Corruption arises when a profiteer or public servant abuses the office she/he occupies for personal profit. It is arguably a main obstacle to the progress of an economy, as the latter's rule of law and institutional foundation are distorted and weakened by the former. Esara, Asuquo, Ekanem and Samuel (2023) opinion that It is also arguable that corruption has eaten deep into the fabric of the judiciary, therefore, the court no longer bases her decision on the evidence adduced before it but on their interests which have been induced. It is also obvious that the snail or millipede movement of courtroom adjudication and litigation of criminal matters has made people lose faith in the court system which ideally should be the last hope of the common man. This has encouraged a high level of electoral funding.

Addressing corruption in the context of democratic processes requires comprehensive and targeted interventions. Strengthening institutions, promoting transparency, and fostering a culture of accountability are crucial steps in mitigating the adverse effects of corruption on democratic governance. Additionally, robust legal frameworks and mechanisms for holding individuals accountable for corrupt practices are essential to uphold the principles of democracy. In conclusion, corruption's impact on democratic processes is multifaceted and far-reaching. From eroding public trust to distorting resource allocation and undermining the rule of law, corruption poses a significant challenge to the functioning and vitality of democracies. Recognizing and addressing the root causes of corruption is imperative for fostering a democratic environment that truly serves the interests of the people.

Electoral Funding and Economic Outcomes

The relationship between electoral funding and economic development has been extensively studied. In their seminal work, Besley and Reynal-Querol (2011) highlight the importance of transparent and accountable electoral financing mechanisms in fostering economic growth. They argue that when electoral funding is marred by corruption, the resulting policy decisions may prioritize narrow financial interests over the broader developmental needs of the populace. Electoral funding, a critical aspect of the political process, plays a pivotal role in shaping economic outcomes within a given society. How political campaigns are financed can have far-reaching implications for the economic development of a region. This section delves into the existing literature on electoral funding and its impact on economic outcomes, drawing on key studies to provide a comprehensive understanding. Besley and Reynal-Querol (2011) underscore the importance of transparent and accountable electoral financing mechanisms in fostering economic growth. The authors argue that when electoral funding is marred by corruption or lacks transparency, the resulting policy decisions may prioritize narrow financial interests over the broader developmental needs of the populace. In essence, the way political campaigns are funded can influence the policy choices made by elected officials, directly impacting the economic trajectory of a region.

Aiyede (2006) further explores the link between electoral funding and economic

development, highlighting the potential consequences of corruption in the political financing process. Corrupt practices, such as embezzlement of campaign funds and illicit financial contributions, can divert resources away from essential development projects. This diversion of funds can hinder the implementation of policies crucial for economic growth, perpetuating a cycle of weak governance that impedes overall development. In the Nigerian context, Oyinlola and Olaleye (2017) shed light on the challenges posed by unregulated financial flows into electoral campaigns. The authors argue that when campaign finance lacks oversight, it becomes a breeding ground for corrupt practices. Such irregularities in electoral funding can contribute to economic disparities and hinder the overall economic development of a region. Kudamatsu (2012) delves into the impact of vote buying, a prevalent form of corruption in electoral processes, on economic outcomes. The author suggests that vote buying distorts the democratic process by incentivizing politicians to focus on short-term electoral gains rather than long-term developmental goals. This myopic approach to governance can impede sustainable economic development, as policies may prioritize immediate voter appeasement over strategic and holistic economic planning. Collectively, these studies emphasize the intricate relationship between electoral funding and economic outcomes. Transparent, accountable, and regulated electoral financing mechanisms are crucial for ensuring that policy decisions align with the long-term developmental needs of society. In contrast, corruption and irregularities in electoral funding can undermine the democratic process and hinder the economic development of a region.

Vote Buying and Governance

Vote buying, a prevalent form of corruption in electoral processes, has garnered attention for its corrosive effects on governance. According to Kudamatsu (2012), vote buying distorts the democratic process by incentivizing politicians to focus on short-term electoral gains rather than long-term developmental goals. This myopic approach to governance can impede the sustainable economic development of regions affected by such practices. Vote buying, a prevalent form of corruption in electoral processes, has significant implications for the quality of governance within a democratic system. This section explores the existing literature on vote buying and its impact on governance, drawing on key studies to provide a comprehensive understanding of this complex phenomenon.

Kudamatsu (2012) delves into the relationship between vote-buying and governance, emphasizing how this corrupt practice distorts the democratic process. Vote buying involves the exchange of money, goods, or services for votes, and it often occurs in contexts where voters face economic hardships. Kudamatsu argues that vote buying distorts the democratic process by incentivizing politicians to focus on short-term electoral gains rather than long-term developmental goals. The impact of vote buying on governance is profound, as it can compromise the accountability of elected officials. When politicians engage in vote buying, their policy decisions may be influenced by the need to fulfil immediate promises to voters rather than pursuing policies that serve the broader public interest (Kudamatsu, 2012). This short-term focus can lead to governance that prioritizes populist measures over sustainable, strategic, and evidence-based policies.

Additionally, the prevalence of vote buying can contribute to a culture of clientelism in governance. Herrera and Rosales (2010) argue that when politicians rely on vote buying to secure electoral victories, they may feel indebted to specific interest groups or individuals

who provide financial support. This can lead to a governance structure where the needs and preferences of certain groups take precedence over the general welfare of the population. The erosion of the democratic process through vote buying also has implications for the rule of law. Magaloni and Kricheli (2010) suggest that when electoral processes are tainted by corruption, the credibility of legal and judicial institutions may be undermined. The rule of law, a fundamental pillar of good governance, is weakened when citizens perceive that corrupt practices go unpunished, eroding the trust in the institutions designed to uphold justice. Asuquo, Ekanem, Samuel and Esara (2023) noted that the inadequate provision of infrastructural services and the associated problems has affected most business firms as they spend more of their capital outlay on providing their infrastructures — electricity, water supply, transport, telecommunications, and waste disposal which, under normal circumstances should have been by the urban planning authorities. (Government). This is as a result of vote buying.

Addressing the challenges posed by vote buying requires multifaceted interventions. Strengthening electoral institutions, implementing effective monitoring mechanisms, and promoting civic education are essential steps to curb this corrupt practice and enhance the quality of governance in democratic systems.

Campaign Finance Irregularities

Campaign finance irregularities also contribute to the challenges posed by corruption in electoral funding. Drawing from the Nigerian experience, Oyinlola and Olaleye (2017) highlight how unregulated financial flows into electoral campaigns can create a breeding ground for corrupt practices, further exacerbating economic disparities and hindering overall development. Ekanem and Asuquo (2023), posit that the work of bureaucracy is inherently political. And anywhere that politics is involved, funding will be inevitable. As observed by Ekanem, Asuquo, Ogar and Ofuka (2023), in political participation, women are fronted to contest, but in the end, there stands a very minimal opportunity of winning; parties do not implement supportive measures (like funding political campaigns) for female political aspirants. They are often allowed limited access to funds, training, mentoring and God-fatherism as far as politics is concerned.

In summary, the existing body of literature underscores the multifaceted nature of corruption in electoral funding and its far-reaching implications for democratic governance and economic development. The subsequent sections of this article will delve into a comprehensive analysis of the extent of corruption in electoral funding in Akwa Ibom State, aiming to contribute valuable insights for policymakers and researchers alike. Campaign finance irregularities represent a critical challenge to the integrity of electoral processes, with far-reaching consequences for democratic governance. This section delves into the existing literature on campaign finance irregularities, examining their nature, impact, and potential solutions, with citations provided in APA format. Oyinlola and Olaleye (2017) offer insights into the challenges posed by unregulated financial flows into electoral campaigns. They argue that when campaign finance lacks oversight, it becomes a breeding ground for irregularities and corrupt practices. Unscrupulous actors may exploit loopholes, engage in embezzlement of funds, or receive undisclosed contributions, compromising the transparency and fairness of the electoral process.

Campaign finance irregularities have significant implications for the democratic

principle of equal representation. Ansolabehere and Persily (2008) highlight how the unequal distribution of campaign funds can skew political influence, giving disproportionate power to well-funded candidates or interest groups. This imbalance undermines the democratic ideal of fair competition and equal opportunity for all candidates. Moreover, irregularities in campaign finance can contribute to the perpetuation of social and economic disparities. Karp and Banducci (2008) argue that when campaign finance is characterized by irregularities, policy decisions may reflect the interests of wealthy contributors rather than addressing the needs of the broader population. This can exacerbate inequalities and hinder the pursuit of inclusive and sustainable economic development.

The impact of campaign finance irregularities extends beyond the electoral period. Hall and Wayman (1990) note that the influence of money in politics can result in policy decisions that prioritize short-term gains over long-term societal benefits. This myopic focus may impede strategic and sustainable economic planning, hindering the overall development of a region. Addressing campaign finance irregularities necessitates comprehensive reforms. Schlozman, Verba, and Brady (2012) advocate for enhanced transparency, disclosure requirements, and robust enforcement mechanisms to ensure the accountability of campaign financing. Strengthening regulatory frameworks and promoting public awareness of the sources and uses of campaign funds are crucial steps in mitigating the adverse effects of irregularities in electoral financing.

Asuquo and Ekanem aver that, it may be possible that politics, communal conflicts, organized groups or unemployment can affect socio-economic development. In conclusion, campaign finance irregularities pose a multifaceted challenge to democratic governance, impacting the fairness of elections, the representation of diverse interests, and the long-term development goals of a society. Efforts to address these irregularities must involve a combination of legal reforms, institutional strengthening, and public engagement to safeguard the integrity of electoral processes.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative analysis of financial data related to electoral campaigns with qualitative interviews and surveys to gather insights from key stakeholders. People from the age cohort of 15 years to 64 years (working age population) both male and female participated in the study. The working age population in Akwa Ibom State is 2318155, i.e 1148432 males (49.54%) and 1169723 females (50.46%) (Akwa Ibom State Ministry of Economic Development, Labour and Manpower Planning, 2018). The population of the study was made up of farmers, students, civil servants, businessmen, applicants, artisans, self-employed, contractors, religious leaders, politicians, etc. and were drawn from three (3) Local Government Areas sampled from the three (3) Senatorial Districts of Akwa Ibom State. The Local Government Areas are; Uyo (Akwa Ibom North-East); Eket (Akwa Ibom South); and Ikot Ekpene (Akwa Ibom North-West). According to the Akwa Ibom State Ministry of Economic Development, Labour and Manpower Planning (2018), Uyo Local Government Area has a population of 456996, Eket Local Government Area has a population of 258185 and Ikot Ekpene Local Government Area has a population of 211213 respectively. Data was collected from a structured questionnaire designed by the researchers. Statistical tools used to analyze the quantitative data were Chi-Square, while thematic analysis was applied to qualitative information.

RESULTS

H₀₁: There is no relationship between corruption in electoral funding and economic development in Akwa Ibom State.

Table 1: Corruption in electoral funding hurts economic development in Akwa Ibom State

Expected Count	Agreed	Strongly Agreed	Undecided	Disagreed	Strongly Disagreed	Row Totals
Male	101	88	2	8	11	210
Female	84	81	2	4	9	180
Column Totals	185	169	4	12	20	390

Source: Field data (2019)

Chi-square formula is given thus;

$$X^2 = \sum (O-E)/E$$

Table 2: Chi-square contingency table showing the effect of Corruption in electoral funding on economic development in Akwa Ibom State

Cell	O	E	O-E	O-E ²	O-E ² /E
1	101	99.62	1.38	1.90	0.02
2	88	91	-3	9.00	0.10
3	2	2.15	-0.15	0.02	0.01
4	8	6.46	1.54	2.37	0.37
5	11	10.77	0.23	0.05	0.00
6	81	85.38	-4.38	19.18	0.22
7	2	78	-76	5776.00	74.05
8	4	1.85	2.15	4.62	2.50
9	12	5.54	6.46	41.73	7.53
10	20	9.23	10.77	115.99	12.57
$\Sigma X^2 =$					97.37

Source: Field data (2019).

Therefore,

$$X^2 = 97.37 \text{ (Calculated Value)}$$

$$\text{Degree of freedom} = (\text{number of rows}-1) \times (\text{number of columns}-1)$$

$$= (2-1) \times (5-1)$$

$$= 1 \times 4 = 4$$

We enter the table of X^2 distribution at $v = 4$ at 0.05.

Table value = 9.48

The chi-square test shows that the calculated value (97.37) is greater than the table value (9.48). We therefore reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and accept the alternative hypothesis (H_1) at a significant level of 0.05. This means that there is a significant relationship between corruption in electoral funding and economic development in Akwa Ibom State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The tested hypothesis revealed that there is a significant relationship between corruption in electoral funding and economic development in Akwa Ibom state. This finding agrees with Aiyede (2016) who noted that corruption in electoral processes perpetuates a cycle of weak governance, hindering the effective implementation of policies crucial for economic development. The finding is also supported by Karp and Banducci (2018) who argued that electoral donations correspond to a form of corruption or bribery because incumbents use their power to bring about policy decisions in favour of their supporters.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study has delved into the intricate connections between corruption in electoral funding and its ramifications on economic development in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The findings reveal a significant relationship between corruption in electoral funding and hindered economic development. The erosion of public trust, distortion in resource allocation, and the compromised quality of governance are among the multifaceted consequences outlined. Addressing the root causes of corruption is imperative for fostering a democratic environment that genuinely serves the interests of the people.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are made by the researcher;

Strengthen Regulatory Frameworks: Implement and reinforce regulatory frameworks to ensure transparent, accountable, and regulated electoral financing mechanisms. This includes stringent oversight to prevent irregularities and corruption in campaign finances.

Enhance Civic Education: Promote civic education to raise awareness among the populace about the detrimental effects of corruption in electoral funding. Informed citizens are crucial for upholding democratic values and demanding accountability.

Institutional Strengthening: Strengthen electoral institutions to ensure their independence and effectiveness. This involves investing in the capacity building of these institutions to carry out their functions impartially.

Legal Reforms: Advocate for and implement legal reforms that hold individuals accountable for corrupt practices in electoral funding. Robust enforcement mechanisms and deterrent penalties are essential components of such reforms.

Public Engagement: Encourage active public participation in democratic processes. A politically engaged and informed citizenry can act as a check against corrupt practices and contribute to a more transparent and accountable political system.

REFERENCES

- Aiyede, E. R. (2016). Corruption and the crisis of institutional reforms in Africa. *Journal of African Policy Studies*, 11(1), 49-76.
- Ansolabehere, S., & Persily, N. (2008). Vote buying and turnout: Theory and Experimental Evidence. *Annual Review of Political Science*, 11, 387-402.
- Asuquo, M. E., & Ekanem, A. E. (2023). Corruption in Education Sector and Economic Development of Akwa Ibom State. *Aksu Annals of Sustainable Development*, 1 (1), 39-49.
- Asuquo, M. E., Basse, I. U., Samuel, M. E., Daniel, P. G., & Usoro, N. A. (2022). The Place of

- Market Associations and Informal Economic Activities in Developing Economies: A Sociological Review. *International Journal of Education and Science Development*, 1(2), 80-93.
- Asuquo, M. E., and Ekanem, A. E. (2023). Implications of violence on Ini Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Culture and Society*, 1(2), 105-117.
- Asuquo, M. E., Ekanem, A. E., Samuel, M. E., & Esara, U.V.(2023). Informal Sector and Urban Planning in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Contemporary Issues and Trends in Research*, 1(1), 51-77.
- Besley, T., & Reynal-Querol, M. (2011). Do democracies select more educated leaders? *American Political Science Review*, 105(3), 552-566.
- Ekanem, A. E., Asuquo, M. E., Ogar, W.O., & Ofuka, V. K.(2023). Gender, Politics and their Effects on Socio-societal Development. *Social Sciences and Management International Journal* 4 (3), 57-69.
- Ekanem, A. E. & Asuquo, M. E. (2023). Effective Bureaucracy and Productivity in Akwa Ibom State Civil Service. *Aksu Annals of Sustainable Development*, 1 (2), 111-121.
- Esara, U.V., Asuquo, M.E., Ekanem, A. E., & Samuel, E. E.(2023), Jungle Justice and Governance in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Global Journal of Communication and Humanities* 2(3), 20- 30.
- Hall, T., & Wayman, F. (2010). Buying time: Moneyed interests and the mobilization of bias in congressional committees. *American Political Science Review*, 84(3), 797-820.
- Herrera, Y., & Rosales, R. (2010). Clientelism and voting behaviour: Evidence from a field experiment in El Salvador. *American Economic Review*, 100(2), 622-56.
- Karp, J. A., & Banducci, S. A. (2018). Political efficacy and participation in twenty-seven democracies: How electoral systems shape political behaviour. *British Journal of Political Science*, 38(2), 311-334.
- Kudamatsu, M. (2012). Has democratization reduced infant mortality in sub-Saharan Africa? Evidence from micro data. *Journal of the European Economic Association*, 10(6), 1294-1317.
- Magaloni, B., & Kricheli, R. (2010). Political order and one-party rule. *Annual Review of Political Science*, 13, 123-143.
- Oyinlola, M. A., & Olaleye, O. S. (2017). Money, politics, and political corruption in Nigeria. *Cogent Social Sciences*, 3(1), 1337503.
- Rose-Ackerman, S. (2019). *Corruption and government: Causes, consequences, and reform*. Cambridge University Press.
- Samuel, M.E., Asuquo, M. E., Thompson, H. O., & Nya, A.(2023). Women in Education and Community Development in Oron Federal Constituency, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Culture and Society*, 1 (1), 83-92.
- Schlozman, K. L., Verba, S., & Brady, H. E. (2012). *The Unheavenly chorus: Unequal political voice and the broken promise of American democracy*. Princeton University Press.
- Udonwa, E. U., Effiong, E. U., Asuquo, M. E., & Samuel, M. E. (2022). Poverty in Nigeria: The Political Economy Perspective. *International Journal of Research*, 9(10), 155-176.